

HOW TO TEACH CHILDREN ENGLISH BY VIDEOS

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Annotation. Modern children cannot imagine their lives without videos. Various devices are embedded in our daily lives and they largely determine how the entire generation receives information. Nowadays, parents are not surprised that the first toy their children get their hands on is a tablet. Furthermore, most adults gain a great benefit from videos which can help to increase their listening and speaking skills. It is undeniable fact that a wide range of videos can encourage students for such pronunciation which is similar to native people.

Key words and expressions: children, adults, knowledge, video, language environment, learning process

Firstly, children are visual learners. Secondly, such children are very pragmatic, and the most important question for them is "How to use the acquired knowledge in life?" Thirdly, if these children are interested in something, they will be determined to achieve their goals. But it is not easy to interest them. Fourthly, their thinking and perception is not focused on remembering facts and details, but on where to find the necessary information and how to apply it in the future.

Thus, visibility plays a crucial role in the learning process. It is easier to remember things that evoke bright feelings and impressions. It is better to get knowledge during interaction. Therefore, video content and cartoons play an important role in the formation of high-quality and effective education. Especially when teaching a foreign language, cartoons are a great resource for learning English! The use of video films in the process of language learning is, first of all, an example of live communication. However, it's not just audio recordings. We see

who is speaking in the videos. We see intonation and facial expressions and gestures that help us understand the general situation.

For children learning English, these cartoons create a real language environment. Children begin to understand that they are the same girl and boy with their mother and father and that they have the same life; they speak differently, but they still understand each other. Any visual sequence that accompanies the speech brings the information closer to the viewer. Regional and cultural facts are not just a collection of phrases, but also create associations, thoughts and a desire to know more about the subject. Visual images encourage you to go to the places in question, taste food (if the conversation is about local culinary traditions), participate in a celebration or visit a museum. The peculiarities of this country will be personally significant; they encourage people to learn English - to learn more, you need to know the language better.

Watching videos and TV shows

Watching a video/TV series - episodes are usually much shorter than movies. Your child will learn about the characters and how they talk. This repetition is very useful for learning.

lots of visuals that show what is being said

clear pronunciation, not too fast

many repetitions of languages

good picture and sound quality.

english learning activity - while watching the show

The purpose of the demonstration is to develop listening skills, specifically "listening for general information." Before the game begins, we can ask our child, "What do you think will happen in this episode?" Now stop the episode and ask your child, "Are you right?"

"Use the questions to check your understanding. For example:

"What happened?"

"Why did they do that?"

"How do you think they feel?"

"What do you think will happen next?"

Such kind of questions can help to understand videos fully and completely.

As for adults, the videos can play an important role for learning different skills. In other words, watching videos helps your students develop their listening comprehension skills and then encourages them to share their thoughts on the topic, talk about their experiences, and connect personally with the topic. These are essential skills for any language learner. Although watching videos is considered a passive activity, videos are often full of content that can be active. Basically, they provoke a reaction from students and can inspire students to share their thoughts on the topic or topics shown in the video, and they help plant the seeds for a great classroom discussion. In other words, watching videos helps your students develop their listening comprehension skills and then encourages them to share their thoughts on the topic, talk about their experiences, and connect personally with the topic. These are essential skills for any language learner. Video is also used as a medium of artistic and creative expression, often telling a story that allows the viewer to make a special emotional connection with the content. Emotion often leads to motivation, inspiration and creative expression. Student engagement with video viewing is greater than reading text and is a means of providing a balanced learning experience involving passive and active student participation.

Here are five ways video can have a powerful impact on teaching and learning:

- **Engagement:** Research has shown that video learning has positive outcomes on many levels, including increased motivation and deeper learning, and can influence students' ability to facilitate discussions and identify problems.
- **Effectiveness:** Video learning is effective on both sides of the classroom; teachers can use it to create time and space for active learning. Once a video is created, it can be reused and updated as needed, freeing up more time for lively classroom discussions and student interaction.

- Authenticity: Video brings the student and teacher one-on-one without even being in the same room. An interesting 2016 study by the Online Learning Consortium found that video helped teachers build and strengthen authentic relationships with students.
- Inspired Thinking: Visual cues, along with audio, play a major role in understanding and retaining new material. According to Forrester Research analyst James McQuivey, one minute of video is equivalent to about 1.8 million written words. Thus, when video is used in the classroom, students are forced to think critically when familiarizing themselves with complex content.

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